

Expert Interview Guides for Evaluating Digital Ethics

Carla Barrio^a, José Juan Osés-Bermejo^b, Vicente Díaz-Gandasegui^c

^a National University of Distance Education (UNED, Spain)

^{b, c} University Carlos III of Madrid (UC3M, Spain)

Traducido con DeepL

MIRATAR ETHICS (Technocare Devices)

Aim of the article: To explore and establish a dialogue between the discourses on digital ethics in the context of health, techno-care and well-being of the medical, IT and sociological teams of the MIRATAR project, in order to investigate from a critical and multidisciplinary perspective the ethical consequences and main considerations to be incorporated into the project without losing sight of the concrete application of these elements in the device.

Aim of the interviews: to provide a background to inform and contextualize the debate and ethical implications taking place within the MIRATAR project. The interviews seek to establish a dialogue between the different disciplines involved in the design and implementation of the pilot, while at the same time offering some initial suggestions for working from an ethical perspective which, we hope, will serve as a contribution to the general debate on the path to follow during the design of these devices. Far from proposing taxative or universal ethical solutions to this debate, the aim is to present an exercise in applied ethics.

Informed consent UC3M (signature on paper or digital)

Interview dates:

Interviewer	Interviewee	Area	Date	Format
		Computing		
		Computing		
		Medicine		
		Medicine		
		Sociology		
		Sociology		

(A) Computer scientists

Block 0. Introduction

- Introduction of the interviewer, purpose of the interview and explanation of the procedure
- Consent
- Acknowledgement to the interviewee for his or her participation

Block I. Presentation of the expert

- Could you briefly describe your experience in the of informatics? Do you have previous experience in the development of health/care technologies? What kind of lessons did you learn from your participation in similar projects?
- In your own words, could you tell me what MIRATAR is for you? If you know of other similar technologies, how does the MIRATAR device differ from those already on the market?
- What is your role in the project?
- From your perspective, how do you understand the relationship between technology and health/care in the challenges of today's society (e.g. hollowed-out Spain, ageing, etc.)?

Block II. MIRATAR devices

- How would you describe the needs that the MIRATAR device seeks to meet?
You mentioned independence, you talked about quality of life... autonomy...
- What do you think is the impact of MIRATAR on the daily life and health of older people?
- What about the people they care for?

Block III. Privacy and security

- There is a strong multidisciplinary debate building in the literature right now around ethics and technology, so as a computer scientist what do you think is the scope of that debate and what is its relevance to research?
- In your opinion, what ethical issues and challenges have arisen as a result of the monitoring and data collection carried out by MIRATAR so? How have these challenges been addressed within the project?
- Beyond legality, have you considered any scenario in which MIRATAR could compromise the privacy, intimacy and security of users? What mechanisms are incorporated to ensure this right?

To explore: how they understand informed consent (capacitism, types of consent, etc.); what discourses they present in relation to ethical committees; what ethical decision-making processes they apply; what data confidentiality means to computer scientists; where third parties who may enter the home are placed; what mechanisms are in place so that data can be deleted from the system; is there any mechanism to consult the data; biases and classifications; what is the best way to ensure that the data can be deleted from the system; is there any mechanism to consult the data; are there any mechanisms in place to ensure that the data can be consulted; are there any mechanisms in place to ensure that the data can be deleted from the system?

Block IV: Relationship between users, technology and health and technology in care

- To what extent do you think the design of the MIRATAR technology takes into account the digital skills disparity of users in the configuration of the device and its functionalities (consent)? To what extent do you work with socio-demographic differences such as race or gender during the design of the device? What (other) strategies are applied to ensure that technologies are equitable and accessible?
- In the literature we have reviewed, there is talk of the undesired, or even perverse, effects of technologies on users. Do you think that the use of MIRATAR can trigger this type of undesired

effects on the emotional management or psychophysical health of users?

Can you give some examples? How have they been dealt with?

- From a design point of view, how do you think the use of these technologies can affect care relationships? What criteria were considered when defining the avatar (physical, voice, type of interaction) and what did you discard and why?

Block V: Challenges of using MIRATAR

- What ethical challenges may arise from heavy reliance on technocare devices rather than direct human care?

We refer to issues such as: deinstitutionalization (personalization/individualization): positive and negative elements

- There is a strong debate about who bears responsibility for negligence that may arise from digital technologies (e.g. cars). How are these issues dealt with in computer science, and is this taken into account in the design of devices?
- What issues have you learned during the development of MIRATAR that may be relevant to the design of future technocare devices?
- What trends do you anticipate at the intersection of technology and care in the future? What role do you see for *machine learning* or AI applied to medical technology?

Closure:

- Is there anything else you would like to add in relation to ethics and technocare devices?
- Final thanks for their time and participation in the interview.

(B) Doctors

Block 0. Introduction

- Introduction of the interviewer, purpose of the interview and explanation of the procedure
- Consent
- Acknowledgement to the interviewee for his or her participation

Block I. Presentation of the expert

- Could you briefly describe your experience in the medical field? Do you have experience working with technologies that support digitized and personalized healthcare? What kind of lessons did you learn from your participation in similar projects?
- In your own words, could you tell me what MIRATAR is for you? If you know of other similar technologies, how does the MIRATAR device differ from those already on the market?
- What is your role in the project?
- From your perspective, how do you understand the relationship between technology, health and care in the challenges of today's society (e.g. hollowed-out Spain, ageing, etc.)?
- How do you think the digitalization and personalization proposed by the Digital Health Strategy recently launched by the Ministry of Health is affecting the development of clinical practice and the quality of care received by patients?

Block II. MIRATAR device

- How would you describe the needs that the MIRATAR device tries to meet?
You've mentioned... you've talked about...
- What do you think is the impact of MIRATAR on the daily life and health of older people?
- What about the people they care for?

Block III. Privacy and security

- What is the scope of this debate and what is its relevance in terms of research challenges? What are the ethical challenges posed or entailed by the digitization of healthcare from MIRATAR devices? How have these challenges been medically addressed within the project?
- Beyond legality, have you considered any scenario in which MIRATAR could compromise the privacy, intimacy and security of users' sensitive medical data?

To explore: how they understand informed consent (capacitism, types of consent, etc.); what discourses they present in relation to ethical committees; what ethical decision-making processes they apply; what data confidentiality means to computer scientists; where third parties who may enter the home come in; biases and classifications.

Block IV: Relationship between users, technology and health

- To what extent do you think that the design of the MIRATAR technology takes into account the digital skills gap of users in the configuration of the device and its functionalities (consent)?
- As a specialist, who do you think should be responsible for explaining how to use these technologies and ensuring that they are used correctly?
A review of the literature on digital ethics in the medical field raises some questions about the effects of normality in the design of devices and their use in consultations. In this line, we would like to ask you as medical professionals to what extent the use of this device can be equitable considering these issues. Does this affect working with specific medical specificities?
- The literature we have reviewed speaks of the unintended, or even perverse, effects of technologies on users.
- What kind of undesirable effects on the emotional management or psychophysical health

of users? Can you give an example? As a medical specialist, how do you think these issues can be addressed?

Other undesirable effects:

- Excessive alarms for caregivers or doctors
 - Risk of self-diagnosis by patients despite indications or transmission indications. How are these issues addressed in the design (e.g. hypochondriasis)?
- And with regard to the avatar, what effects do you think it can have on patients? What do you think this avatar should look like and what functions should it fulfil?

Block V: Challenges of using MIRATAR

- What ethical challenges may arise from heavy reliance on technocare devices instead of face-to-face human medical care?
We refer to issues such as: deinstitutionalization (personalization/individualization): positive and negative elements
- There is a strong debate about who is responsible for the negligence that can arise from digital technologies (e.g. car), how do you deal with these issues in the medical? Do you think this debate is taken into account during the design phases of devices (e.g. wrong dose)?
- What issues have you learned so far with MIRATAR that may be relevant for the design of future technocare devices?
- What trends do you anticipate at the intersection of technology and healthcare in the future? What role do you see for AI in medical technology?

Supporting questions:

- As a doctor, do you have access to information related to ontology and the databases that support these devices?

Closure:

- Is there anything else you would like to add in relation to ethics and technocare devices?
- Final thanks for their time and participation in the interview.

(C) Sociologists

Block 0. Introduction

- Introduction of the interviewer, purpose of the interview and explanation of the procedure
- Consent
- Acknowledgement to the interviewee for his or her participation

Block I. Presentation of the expert

- Could you briefly describe your experience in the field of sociology? Do you have experience working with technologies that support digitized and personalized health care? What kind of lessons did you learn from your participation in similar projects?
- In your own words, could you tell me what MIRATAR is for you? If you know of other similar technologies, how does the MIRATAR device differ from those already on the market?
- What is your role in the project?
- From your perspective, how do you understand the relationship between technology, health and care in the challenges of today's society (e.g. hollowed-out Spain, ageing, etc.)?
- How do you see digitalization and personalization of health affecting care?

Block II. MIRATAR device

- How would you describe the needs that the MIRATAR device tries to meet?
You've mentioned... you've talked about...
- What do you think is the impact of MIRATAR on the daily life and health of older people?
- What about the people they care for?

Block III. Privacy and security

- Right now, there is a multi-disciplinary debate around ethics and technology as sociologists. What is the scope of this debate and what is its relevance in terms of research challenges?
- What ethical challenges does the digitization of healthcare from devices such as MIRATAR pose or entail?
- Beyond legality, have you considered any scenario in which MIRATAR could compromise the privacy, intimacy and security of users' sensitive data?

To explore: how they understand informed consent (capacitism, types of consent, etc.); what discourses they present in relation to ethical committees; what ethical decision-making processes they apply; what data confidentiality means to computer scientists; where third parties who may enter the home come in; biases and classifications.

Block IV: Relationship between users, technology and health

- In the light of your experience in the field of technocare, what requirements do you think MIRATAR should meet in order to be an equitable technology? How can these issues be addressed?
- What gender and racial considerations do you think should be included in the design of such devices?
- What other similar equity-related issues do you think these types of devices; their designs, algorithms, *big data* can generate?
- In the literature we have reviewed, there is talk of the undesired, or even perverse, effects of technologies on users. Do you think that the use of devices such as MIRATAR can trigger this type of undesired effects on emotional management or psychophysical health users? Can you give an example? As a sociology specialist, how do you think these issues can be addressed?
Other undesirable effects:

- Excessive alarms for caregivers or doctors
- Risk of self-diagnosis by patients despite indications or transmission indications. How are these issues addressed in the design (e.g. hypochondriasis)?
- And regarding the use of avatars, what effects do you think they can have on users? What do you think this avatar should look like and what functions should it fulfil?

Block V: Challenges of using MIRATAR

- What ethical challenges may arise from heavy reliance on technocare devices instead of face-to-face human medical care?
We refer at specifically issues such as: deinstitutionalization (personalization/individualization) - positive and negative elements
- What issues have you learned so far with MIRATAR that may be relevant for the design of future technocare devices?
- What trends do you anticipate at the intersection of technology and healthcare in the future? What role do you see for AI in medical technology?

Closure:

- Is there anything else you would like to add in relation to ethics and technocare devices?
- Final thanks for their time and participation in the interview.